

692 kg nonexchangeable K/ha, and 79.70 kg exchangeable Na/ha.

The field experiments were laid out in a random block design with three replications. K was applied as muriate of potash at 0 (K₀), 62.2 (K_{50%}), 83.0 (K_{66%}), and 124.5 (K_{100%}) kg/ha. In 1990, Na was applied as common salt at 0 (K₀), 62 (Na_{33%}), 93 (Na_{50%}), and 186 (Na_{100%}) kg NaCl/ha (Na was chemically equivalent to K); in 1991, it was applied as 83.3 (Na_{33%}), 250 (Na_{100%}), and 375 (Na_{150%}) kg NaCl/ha (NaCl rates were equal to KCl rates). The crop also received 150 kg N/ha as urea and 19.8 kg P/ha as single superphosphate. Plant samples at full heading and ripening stages were analyzed to determine contents of N (Kjeldahl method), K (H₂SO₄-H₂O₂ digestion-ICP method), Na (1 N HCl extraction-ICP method), SiO₂ (H₂SO₄-H₂O₂ digestion-weighting method), and Cl (Mohr method).

Applying Na up to 250 kg NaCl/ha (Na_{100%}) significantly increased grain yield by 4-8% compared with that of the

Table 1. Yields of three rice types grown with and without K and Na fertilizers.^a Zhejiang, China. 1990-91.

Yield	(t/ha)			
	1990		1991	
	Late rice season		Late rice season	
	Hybrid	Indica	Japonica	Hybrid
K ₀ (control)	6.7 a	6.0 a	6.7 a	8.7 a
K _{100%}	7.9 e	6.6 d	7.6 b	10.2 c
Na _{100%}	7.0 b	6.3 bc	7.0 a	9.4 b
Na _{150%}		6.1 a	6.8 a	9.4 b
K _{50%} Na _{50%}	7.4 c	6.4 c	7.3 b	9.9 c
K _{66%} Na _{33%}	7.6 d	6.1 b	7.4 b	10.0 c
CV (%)	6.1	3.5	4.9	5.9

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. The substitution of Na for K was chemically equivalent in 1990 and equal to the salt rates of NaCl to KCl in 1991.

no K and Na application control. The combined application of Na and K (K_{50%} and Na_{50%}, and K_{66%} and Na_{50%} plots) gave almost the same grain yields as the K_{100%} plot in the 1991 late rice crop (Table 1). Applying NaCl usually increased N, SiO₂, Na, and Cl contents in rice plants, perhaps because more dry matter was

produced with Na application than in the control (Table 2).

Applying NaCl did not markedly increase rice plants' uptake of K, and oversupplying NaCl (Na_{150%} plot in 1991 early rice crop) obviously reduced rice plants' K uptake, showing the antagonistic effect between Na and K uptake. ■

Table 2. Nutrient uptake of rice^a as influenced by applying common salt.^b Zhejiang, China. 1990-91.

Treatment	Nutrient uptake (kg/ha)														
	N			K			SiO ₂			Na			Cl		
	G	S	T	G	S	T	G	S	T	G	S	T	G	S	T
<i>1990 late rice season</i>															
<i>Hybrid rice</i>															
K ₀	61.4	70.4	131.7	17.9	54.5	72.3	173.4	582.8	756.2	0.5	15.8	16.3	8.3	48.0	56.2
Na _{100%}	70.5	78.8	149.3	23.0	52.5	75.5	216.2	658.7	874.8	0.6	26.6	27.3	10.1	62.1	72.2
<i>1991 early rice season</i>															
<i>Indica rice</i>															
K ₀	92.0	41.3	133.2	28.4	79.2	107.6	176.0	644.6	820.5	0.5	5.6	6.1	8.8	36.5	45.3
Na _{100%}	99.0	34.8	133.8	28.1	68.1	96.2	236.3	668.3	904.5	0.5	8.5	9.0	10.2	35.5	45.7
Na _{150%}	89.9	33.3	123.2	25.7	67.2	92.9	117.9	518.0	695.9	0.4	8.0	8.4	11.5	29.3	40.8

^aG = grain, S = straw, T = total rice plant. ^bIn 1990 experiment, Na_{100%} = 186 kg NaCl/ha. In 1991 experiment, Na_{100%} = 250 kg NaCl/ha, Na_{150%} = 375 kg NaCl/ha.

Fertilizer management — organic sources

Algicides in *Azolla* germplasm management

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The aquatic fern *Azolla* is cultivated as a green manure for application with

lowland rice in parts of Asia and the South Pacific. *Azolla* cultures are commonly maintained in the vegetative phase in germplasm collections. Free-living cyanobacteria and microalgae within the growth medium of the open cultures may contaminate these accessions. Valuable plants may die from frequent infestations if they are not

periodically washed and transferred. The presence of the *Anabaena azollae* symbiont complicates eradicating these phototropic contaminants with biocides.

As a possible solution to this maintenance problem, six *Azolla* species were tested for tolerance for two Cu⁺²-based algicides: copper sulfate and chelated copper (Cutrine-Plus^R, Applied

Biochemists, Inc., Milwaukee, WI, USA). Accessions came from *A. microphylla* (MI-NE KKN3), *A. mexicana* (ME-UCD 62), *A. caroliniana* (CA 3007), *A. filiculoides* (FI 1514), *A. pinnata* var. *imbricata* (PI 0509), and *A. nicolata* (NI 5001).

Several Cu²⁺ concentrations from 0.1 to > 2.5 ppm of each algicide were added to N-free BG-11 growth medium. Each *Azolla* species was tested for viability and growth. Duplicate 14-d experiments were completed in a laboratory under moderate photon flux densities (100-200 μmol/m² per s) and temperatures (22-25 °C). Glass beakers (400 ml) containing 250 ml of BG-11 were inoculated with 0.5 g fresh weight (FW) of *Azolla*. Evaporated water was replaced as needed. Growth was measured by changes in total chlorophyll and FW.

The effectiveness of both algaecides in decreasing the presence of microbial contaminants in growth media was visually apparent at concentrations of ≥ 0.5 ppm Cu²⁺. Biomass accumulation in all *Azolla* species was slightly reduced at 0.5 ppm (see figure) and was inhibited more at higher concentrations. Viability thresholds of each species were determined to be near 1.0 ppm, where chlorosis of fronds and decreased relative growth rates of FW were observed (see table). The source of Cu²⁺ was not a differentiating factor in the results of most growth trials. Accessions did not survive doses of ≥ 2.5 ppm of either

Combined average data for *Azolla* growth and viability.

algicide. Conversely, applications of 0.1 ppm produced no visible symptoms of stress, and little difference in growth between the treated and control samples in any species (see table).

Amendments of 0.5 ppm Cu²⁺ to growth medium as either copper sulfate or a chelated form were concluded to be potentially useful if incorporated into the maintenance programs of *Azolla* germplasm collections. Plant growth is

stable, signifying a healthy symbiont, and the presence of contaminant populations is diminished. A side effect, however, is stunted root development. This phenomenon was not observed to be harmful to *Azolla* viability in these experiments and may prove to facilitate maintenance. Freely hanging roots often become tangled, thus complicating cleaning. They are also microsites for protists, nematodes, and phototrophic contaminants. ■

Growth of six *Azolla* species in N-free growth medium amended with copper-based algicide.^a

<i>Azolla</i> species	1.0 ppm Cu ²⁺		0.5 ppm Cu ²⁺		0.1 ppm Cu ²⁺		No added Cu ²⁺	
	Total Chl ^b (μmg)	FW ^c (g)	Total Chl (μg)	FW (g)	Total Chl (μg)	FW (g)	Total Chl (μg)	FW (g)
<i>A. microphylla</i>	258.90 (3.27)	0.88 (0.04)	861.08 (12.34)	1.76 (0.07)	786.77 (99.24)	1.86 (0.14)	1043.88 (74.95)	2.15 (0.09)
<i>A. nicolata</i>	389.88 (42.89)	0.88 (0.06)	712.79 (34.47)	1.60 (0.00)	818.03 (41.09)	1.54 (0.04)	889.47 (43.12)	1.74 (0.07)
<i>A. pinnata</i> var. <i>imbricata</i>	681.25 (213.56)	1.25 (0.19)	989.71 (26.39)	1.99 (0.02)	1258.30 (76.04)	2.02 (0.05)	1269.65 (48.09)	2.08 (0.06)
<i>A. caroliniana</i>	227.92 (9.34)	0.73 (0.04)	858.53 (13.03)	1.77 (0.03)	962.71 (111.79)	2.07 (0.17)	1018.42 (75.35)	2.19 (0.11)
<i>A. mexicana</i>	192.13 (13.62)	0.79 (0.02)	704.33 (114.49)	1.62 (0.13)	1086.43 (129.46)	2.26 (0.11)	978.48 (77.03)	2.14 (0.09)
<i>A. filiculoides</i>	291.07 (27.60)	0.92 (0.03)	666.78 (132.10)	1.44 (0.17)	877.68 (125.62)	1.67 (0.12)	879.80 (46.25)	1.82 (0.06)

^a Combined data of both chelated copper and copper sulfate; numbers in parentheses represent standard errors of means. ^b Chl = chlorophyll. ^c FW = fresh weight.